

REDUCING THE NATURAL DECLINE OF APPLES DURING LONG STORAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071405>

Abstract: In this article Samarkand region The apples grown and stored in the limited liability company "Marokand fruit and vegetables" in Jomboy district were treated with methylcyclopropene. 1-methylcyclopropene to reduce apple fruit decline by applying the drug at acceptable rates to apples after long-term storage of Red Delicious, Granny Smith, Scarlet, Pinklady, Golden Delicious, Jiromin, Fuji, Gala and Modi apples, treated with apples aimed at reducing the natural decrease by using the drug.

Key words: apple, storage, 1-methylcyclopropene, hardness, ethylene, controlled atmosphere, commodity analysis, biochemical parameters, natural reduction.

Relevance of experience. Today, the total volume of apple production in the world is more than 80.5 million tons, the leading places are China (respectively 44.45 million tons), USA (4.65 million tons), Poland (3.60 million tons), Turkey (2.93 million tons) and Uzbekistan (1.238 million tons). About 90-95% of apple orchards in the world's leading apple-producing and exporting countries are grown in intensive orchards based on low-growing grafts. In most of the countries where apples are grown, regular research is conducted to create new high-quality commercial varieties of this fruit, to radically increase their production volume, fruit quality and shelf life, in order to gain a prestigious position in the world apple market, which is the most competitive.

The level of study of the problem. Due to the fact that apples do not have the characteristics of long-term storage under normal conditions, it is recommended to store them in warehouses with a controlled gas environment in order to reduce the change in commodity characteristics. The shelf life of an apple fruit depends on its pomological variety, as well as the amount of dry matter in its chemical composition. Air temperature, relative humidity and gas environment in warehouses are the factors that affect their shelf life. A controlled gas environment extends the shelf life of fruits in warehouses by 1.5-2.0 times. Also, apples stored in a controlled gas environment retain more sugar, organic acids, and vitamins than those stored in a conventional manner.

The purpose of the study. Selection of storage-resistant varieties from apples grown in the central regions of Uzbekistan, study of technological features and reduction of natural decline of stored apples.

Research task. Determining the effective method of storage of apple varieties selected for research, researching the technological and biochemical composition of apple varieties, and testing non-traditional methods of pre-treatment in apple storage are defined as the main task of reducing natural decline.

Research objects and methods. Red Delishes, Golden Delishes, Renet Simirenko, Scarlet (Steamored) varieties included in the state register in Uzbekistan and introduced Green Smith, Gala, Pink Lady, Fuji, Modi, Jeromin varieties were selected.

environment (containing 1.5% O₂ and 1.5% CO₂) according to the manual "Refrigeration of products". was conducted. Penitrometer, refractometer, titrimetric, photometric analysis methods were used to determine the optimal level of fruit ripening and biochemical parameters during storage: titratable acids according to GOST ISO 750-2013 ; hardness of apple core with penetrometer FT-372; Determining the release of product varieties according to GOST R 54697-11.

Discussion of results. Experiments were carried out on the preservation and natural reduction rates of improving the pretreatment processes of apples before storing them.

Before storage, a solution of different concentrations of 1-MSP (methylcyclopropene) compound was placed in 4 points for free evaporation for 12-24 hours. This experiment was used to determine the optimal concentration of the 1-MSP drug and monitor the amount of natural reduction of the product.

In this, the marketability and natural decline of apples were evaluated after 180 days of storage in controlled gas atmosphere storage warehouses. By applying the 1-methylcyclopropene compound used in these experiments to the storage chambers at the rates of 0.05 g, 0.08 g, 1.0 g, and 1.03 g, the biochemical composition of apples stored for 220 days remained unchanged, the shelf life , it was considered acceptable to use 1-methylcyclopropene compound at 0.08 g, so that disease resistance, productivity and natural reduction are minimal.

The natural decline of apples placed in a common chamber was monitored by observations in a controlled gas environment (BGM) warehouse for 220 days after different treatments of the apple cultivars put into storage.

simple storage of products placed in controlled gas environment (BGM) warehouse without any processing. The highest natural reduction compared to the total amount during storage for 220 days is in the variety Red deliciouses

(13.9%), Renet Simirenko (14.6%)), Scarlet (Steymored) (14.1 %), Gala (13.8 %) and Jerome (14.6 %) varieties were observed.

Natural shrinkage of apples after different treatments and 220 days of storage in a controlled gas environment

Nº	Varieties	simple method	1st MSP with 0.05%	1st MSP with 0.08%	1st MSP with 1.00%	1st MSP with 1.03%
1	Red Delishes	13.9	9.5	3.2	8.2	8.8
2	Golden Delishes	12.4	8.8	2.6	7.0	8.3
3	Renet Simirenko	14.6	9.9	3.7	7.7	9.2
4	Scarlet (Staymored)	14.1	9.7	3.4	8.3	9.0
5	Granny Smith	12.1	8.7	2.7	7.1	8.5
6	Gala	13.8	9.9	3.4	8.3	8.7
7	Pink Lady	12.2	8.5	2.6	6.8	9.0
8	Fuji	12.6	9.0	3.2	7.5	8.7
9	Modi	13.1	9.5	3.6	7.7	8.5
10	Jerome	14.6	9.9	3.9	7.7	9.2

We can see that the natural shrinkage of the analyzed apple varieties was reduced by 3.4-4.7% compared to the normal method of apple varieties treated with **0.05% 1-methylcyclopropene compound in chambers and stored in a controlled gas environment warehouse for 220 days**. For example. 4.4%, Golden Delishes 3.6%, Renet Simirenko 4.7%, Scarlett (Staymored) 4.4%, Granny Smith 3.4%, Gala 3.9%, Pink Lady 3. .7%, Fuji 3.6%, Modi 3.6%, Jerome 4.7% natural decrease was observed. The natural reduction of stored apples under the influence of the applied 0.05% 1-methylcyclopropene compound was determined from 8.5 to 9.9% of the total amount.

That apple cultivars placed for storage in chambers were treated with **0.08% 1-methylcyclopropene compound and the natural shrinkage of apples stored in a controlled gas environment warehouse for 220 days was significantly reduced by 9.4-10.9% compared to the normal method**. we can reach For example. 10.7%, Golden Delishes 9.8%, Renet Simirenko 10.9%, Scarlet (Steamored) 10.7%, Granny Smith 9.4%, Gala 10.4%, Pink Lady 9. .6%, Fuji 9.4% Modi 9.5%, Jerome 10.7% natural decrease was observed. The natural reduction of stored apples under the influence of the applied 0.08% 1-methylcyclopropene compound was observed from 2.6% to 3.9% natural

reduction in the cross-section of varieties, and the lowest natural reduction in the experimental variants was the 0.08% 1-methylcyclopropene compound. was found to be treated with

The studied apple varieties were treated with **1.0% 1-methylcyclopropene compound in chambers and stored for 220 days in a controlled gas environment warehouse. Compared to the simple method, the natural shrinkage of apples was observed to decrease by 5.0-6.9% in the following varieties.** For example: Red deliciouses 5.7%, Golden Delishes 5.4%, Renet Simirenko 6.9%, Scarlet (Steamored) 5.8%, Granny Smith 5.0%, Gala 5.5%, Pink ledi 5.4%, Fuji 5.1%, Modi 5.4%, Jerome 6.9% natural decrease was observed. The natural reduction of stored apples under the influence of the applied 1.0% 1-methylcyclopropene compound was determined from 6.8 to 8.3% natural reduction compared to the total amount.

Apple varieties suitable for storage were treated in chambers with **1.03% 1-methylcyclopropene compound and stored in a controlled gas environment warehouse for 220 days. Compared to the normal method, the natural shrinkage of apples was observed to decrease by 3.2-5.4% in the following varieties.** For example: Red deliciouses 5.1%, Golden Delishes 4.1%, Renet Simirenko 4.4%, Scarlet (Steamored) 5.1%, Granny Smith 3.6%, Gala 5.1%, Pink ledi 3.2%, Fuji 3.9%, Modi 4.6%, Jerome 5.4% natural decrease was observed. The natural reduction of stored apples under the influence of the applied 1.03% 1-methylcyclopropene compound was determined from 8.3 to 9.2% natural reduction compared to the total amount.

the table , it became clear that the natural reduction of apples stored for 220 days without any treatment in the usual way is from 12.1 to 14.6%, and when treated with 0.05% of 1-methylcyclopropene compound, from 8.5 to 9.9%. 2.6 to 3.9 percent when treated with 0.08 percent 1-methylcyclopropene compound, 6.8 to 8.3 percent when treated with 1.0 percent 1-methylcyclopropene compound, and treated with 1.03 percent 1-methylcyclopropene compound 8.3 to 9.2 percent natural reduction was observed, based on the above data, the lowest natural reduction was observed when applying 0.08 percent 1-methylcyclopropene compound in apple varieties stored for 220 days. In addition, by applying 0.08 percent of 1-methylcyclopropene compound, the natural decrease in storage of apples from 220 days to more than days is realized at a minimum level.

Conclusion. The use of 0.08% preparation of 1-methylcyclopropene drug was shown to be the most optimal technology in the storage of apple fruits. The rate

of natural shrinkage of apples in all varieties was reduced by 3.0-3.5 times compared to the storage of apples without processing in the storage of a normal controlled gas environment. Also, marketability and quality indicators were improved during 220 days of treatment with 0.08% 1-MSP compound when stored in controlled gas environment warehouses .

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